

EFFECTS OF THE ELONGATION PROPERTY OF MATRIX RESIN ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THE FRP

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ABSTRACT

Effects of the elongation property of matrix resin on mechanical properties in continuous strand glass mat reinforced CP-resin(Cross-linked Polyesteramide resin) composites were studied experimentally. The experiments were carried out under static, impact and fatigue tensile loadings, and by observing the macro and micro fracture surfaces. For the purpose of this investigation we used two types CP-resin, the elastic modulus and the tensile strength are nearly of the same values, while the elongation is very different. The composite specimens are made of these resins and glass mats with various fiber contents. It is found that the degree of the effect of the elongation property of matrix resin on the FRP varied in loading type and fiber content, and it affects remarkably the static tensile strength of CP-resin composite but slightly its fracture toughness and fatigue strength.

Keywords: Polyesteramide resin, Continuous strand mat, Mechanical property, Fracture toughness, S-N curve, Acoustic emission.

1. INTRODUCTION

Matrix resin of FRP has been shown to be media both for load transmission to a fiber and for load dispersion in a matrix. Hence characteristics of the FRP are influenced by matrix resin properties. There are many results of noticing the research of the FRP for the behavior of the reinforced fiber, but the research on the effect of matrix resin property is a little. In some examples the following might be used: matrix resin of which the type differs[1], changed properties by the plasticizer[2,3] and different of the molecular structure[4]. However, it is unknown how each property of matrix resin has influence on the property of FRP.

The purpose of this investigation is to examine the role of the matrix resin in the FRP by means of the mechanical properties, fracture behavior and fatigue behavior of the composites as a whole. For this purpose we use two types of CP-resin[5] whose elastic modulus and tensile strength are nearly the same with each other, while their elongations are very different. The composite specimens are made of these resins and continuous-glass-fiber-mats of 20wt.%, 40wt.% and 60wt.% fiber content.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

Test specimens are made of cross-linked polyesteramide resin (CP-resin) and continuous glass strand mat for reinforcing the resin. CP-resin is the thermoset resin, developed by Takeda Chemical Industry, LTD. It consists of 2,2'-(1,3- phenylene) bis-2-oxazolone (1,3-PBO), dibasic acid and catalyst. The properties of CP-resin vary on the type of dibasic and the mole ratio of dibasic acid to 1,3-PBO. Two types of resin were used in the present study. The elastic modulus and the tensile strength for these two resins are of nearly the same values, while their fracture elongation are quite different, i.e., one behaves like a brittle resin (named as H material) and the other one is just like a ductile resin (P material). Continuous strand mats were made of spiral and continuous glass fiber (E-glass, 19 μ m diameter). The fiber weight contents of the specimens were 0, 20, 40 and 60wt.% for both resins, and they are called H0, H20, H40, H60, P0, P20, P40 and P60, respectively.

2.2 Static tensile test

2.2.1 Dumbbell specimen The shape of dumbbell specimen is shown in Fig.1(a). That shape and dimension are based on JIS standard. Two aluminum plates for the target of laser beams are attached to the test specimen so as to measure its displacement.

2.2.2 Test procedure Static tests are performed using a servo-hydraulic testing machine at the crosshead speed of 1mm/min. Axial and transverse strain of the specimen are measured by strain gauge, and the change in the gauge length is measured by the laser displacement meter(Keyence, LB-1000) throughout the test. The tests are performed under a constant temperature and humidity (20 ± 2 , $60 \pm 5\%$ RH).

2.3 Fracture toughness test

2.3.1 SEN specimen In order to obtain fracture toughness, SEN specimen is used. The material used H0 ,H20, H60, P0, P20 and P60. The shape and dimension of the specimen is shown in Fig.1(b). Crack gauge is mounted on the specimen so as to observe crack extension behavior. The notch is carefully cut by a diamond wheel cutter(notch blade, 0.1mm thickness) for both crack gauge and specimen, and notch length a is taken as $1/3$ of the specimen width W . The specimen is reinforced with the steel plate over the loading place to prevent over the initiation of fracture around the holes.

2.3.2 Test procedure Static tests of SEN specimen are performed by the same equipment under the same condition to the tests performed to the dumbbell types. Impact test is carried out by the impact testing machine which consists of the load detective equipment based on One Bar Method[6] and the displacement detector of potentiometer, as shown schematically in Fig.2. The specimen is attached between the output bar(steel, 40mm diameter, 4m length) connected to the fixed end and the crosshead moving on the slide rail. The constant impact speed is 3.1m/s, and the impact load in the specimen is calculated from semiconductor gauge located at a distance 250mm from the fitting hole

of the output bar. Crack initiation and crack extension behaviors are monitored by the crack gauge located at the notch tip. As the loading speed both for the static and the impact testing is comparatively low, the fracture toughness K_s and K_d are calculated by Eq.(1) given by Brown for pin-loading specimen[7].

$$K_s, K_d = \left(\frac{P \sqrt{a}}{BW} \right) f \left(\frac{a}{W} \right) \tag{1}$$

$$f \left(\frac{a}{W} \right) = 1.99 - 0.41 \left(\frac{a}{W} \right) + 18.70 \left(\frac{a}{W} \right)^2 - 38.48 \left(\frac{a}{W} \right)^3 + 53.85 \left(\frac{a}{W} \right)^4$$

where the suffixes s and d imply static and impact condition, P is load, and a, B and W are notch length, thickness and width of the specimen. $f(a/W)$ is the correction factor that depends only on a/W .

2.4 Fatigue test

2.4.1 Specimen The shape of the specimen is dumbbell type to restrict the damage area as shown in Fig.1(c). Used materials are H20, H60, P20 and P60.

2.4.2 Test procedure Fatigue tests are performed using a servo-hydraulic testing machine(Shimadzu, Servo-pulsar) at frequency 2Hz. The applied stress was of tension triangular

Fig.1 Geometric shape and size of the specimen.

wave with the stress ratio 0.1. Damage evaluation under fatigue test was carried out by the AE (acoustic emission) method. Two AE sensors of a wide range type were attached to the specimen in two channels to avoid noise. AE amplitude distribution and AE event count rate are used as AE parameters and the damage processes are discussed by using those parameters.

Fig.2 Schematic of impact testing machine.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Mechanical properties

For each material of H and P, stress-strain curves are shown in Figs.3(a) and 3(b), and elastic modulus E , tensile strength σ_B , elongation and poisson's ratio are shown in table 1. From these figures and table, E and σ_B of both neat resins(H0 and P0) show nearly the same values with each other, but σ_B of P0 is 4 times higher than that of H0.

Fig.3 Stress-strain curves.

For the FRP which consists of these matrix resin, E increases with increasing fiber content expectedly. The values of ϵ_B for both composites of fiber contents 20wt.%, however, are lower than those of both neat resin materials. The tensile strength of the ductile matrix resin FRP is higher by 20 ~ 30% than that of the brittle matrix resin FRP. Thus elongation property of matrix resin contributes to ϵ_B of the FRP. It is likely that the shearing force induced in the P-matrix FRP by difference in elongation between fiber and resin may be lower than that induced in the H-matrix FRP and the fiber in the P-matrix FRP may bear a less burden so that ϵ_B of P-matrix FRP becomes to be higher than that of H-matrix FRP.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of the materials.

Material	Fiber content Wt.%(vol.%)	Elastic modulus E, GPa	Tensile strength σ_B, MPa	Elongation , %	Poisson's ratio
H0	0(0)	4.9	91	2.0	0.33
H20	20(11)	8.2	64	0.8	0.38
H40	40(25)	12.0	114	1.2	0.35
H60	60(43)	16.7	199	1.5	0.32
P0	0(0)	4.6	108	8.0	0.37
P20	20(11)	8.4	95	1.2	0.39
P40	40(25)	12.2	176	2.0	0.34
P60	60(43)	17.1	275	2.5	0.32

3.2 Fracture toughness

3.2.1 Crack extension Figures 4 and 5 show the typical relations between the load-time curves and the crack extension-time curves both for static and impact loading. Observation of crack extension by crack gauge shows that the crack initiates with unstable fracture at Pmax load and goes into final fracture for P0 and H0 materials, as shown in Figs.4(a) and 5(a). For both matrix resin FRP, as shown in Figs.4(b) and 5(b), after crack extends a few mm, crack extension speed changes drastically to that of unstable fracture near the Pmax load. It is found from the observation of the fracture surface inked during the course of testing that these crack extensions at early loading time consist mainly of resin cracking and delamination without fiber breaking. In calculating the fracture toughness by Eq.(1), P and a are taken as Pmax and the initial length of a notch, respectively.

3.2.2 Static and impact fracture toughness Figs.6 and 7 show static fracture toughness Ks and impact fracture toughness Kd obtained by the above method. The values of static and impact fracture toughness(Ks and Kd) increase with increasing fiber content for both matrix resin FRP. Kd for both neat resin materials are less than Ks, but Kd for all FRP are higher than Ks. The fracture toughness of the ductile resin FRP is same or higher than that of the brittle one. Effect of the matrix resin is more

notable in respect to K_s rather than K_d , and influence of the impact speed is most prominent in the case of 20wt.% FRP by the reason that rate of change in K_s and K_d is largest among others.

From the microscopic observation of the SEM, following facts are found. The fracture surface of H0 is rather flat for both static and impact loading, but that the surface of P0 is rough with tear line in comparison with that of H0. From the above fact, it is recognized that K_s and K_d of P0 are higher than those of H0, and that for both neat resin materials, K_s is higher than K_d . As continuous fiber is in the form of spiral and the fiber content is low in the case of 20wt.% FRP, distribution of fiber in a matrix gives a great influence on the morphology of the fracture surface. Over the part where fibers distribute sparsely, the fracture surface is rather flat and we can see resin cracking for H20 material, while the river pattern can be observed for P20 material. On the contrary, over the part where fibers distribute densely or entangle each other, many resin crackings are observed. This tendency is more prominent to H20 material rather than P20 material and also to the impact loading rather than the

Fig.4 Relationship between load-time and crack extension-time curves under static loading.

Fig.5 Relationship between load-time and crack extension-time curves under impact loading.

Fig.6 Relationship between fracture toughness and fiber content under static loading.

Fig.7 Relationship between fracture toughness and fiber content under impact loading.

static one. Thus, morphology of the fracture surface represents difference due to matrix resin, but the value of fracture toughness is almost same or that of P20 material is slightly higher. Hence, it can be concluded that matrix resin has little influence on fracture toughness.

The fracture surface of 60wt.% FRP shows no difference to both matrix resin FRP and both static and impact loading respectively. However, based on the observation of fracture appearance from the side view, which is not indicated here, the pull-out fiber length of the H60 material is longer than that of P60 material and also its length is longer in the case of impact loading rather than static loading. Since P-matrix resin is ductile and accommodates itself to deformation well, the pull-out fiber length of P-matrix resin FRP is shorter than that of H-matrix resin FRP.

3.3 Fatigue strength

3.3.1 S-N curves Fatigue strength will depend on the property of matrix resin. Figure 8 shows the S-N relationship between the maximum applied stress and the number of fracture cycles at the 2Hz frequency. For the 60wt.% FRP with different resins, the S-N curves were similar no matter that the matrix resin is brittle (H-matrix resin) or ductile (P-matrix resin). However, for the 20wt.%FRP, the P20 material had higher fatigue strength than that in H20. This indicates that the deformation property of matrix resin almost wouldn't affect the fatigue strength for a high fiber content material, but it had a great influence on the fatigue strength when the materials are low fiber content. The material with P-matrix resin had higher fatigue strength than that with H-matrix resin.

The strength ratio of fatigue strength at $N=10^6$ to static strength was shown in Table 2. It indicates that the P-matrix material was lower for the fatigue strength ratio for both fiber content 60wt.%, 20wt.% materials and that the effect of the elongation property was small.

3.3.2 Fatigue damage In this study, damage process is estimated by AE amplitude distribution and AE event count rate. Generally, AE event that counted the AE signal by the event count method is correspondent to the damage mode. It was examined the damage mode of the FRP using AE

Fig.8 S-N curves.

Table 2. Strength ratio of the materials.

Material	Static tensile strength, MPa	Fatigue strength at N=10 ⁶ , MPa	Strength ratio*
P60	275	73	0.27
H60	199	73	0.37
P20	95	40	0.42
H20	64	35	0.55

*Strength ratio=fatigue strength at N=10⁶ /static tensile strength.

Fig.9 Relationship between AE event count and AE amplitude of P60 material.

Fig.10 Relationship between AE event count and AE amplitude of H60 material.

(a)
Middle
amplitude

(b)
High
Amplitude

Fig.11 Relationship between AE event count rate and normalized cycles N/N_f of P60 material.

Fig.12 Relationship between AE event count rate and normalized cycles N/N_f of H60 material.

amplitude distribution detected, until the specimen breaks. AE amplitude distribution of the P60 and H60 material in $10^5 < N_f$ are shown in Figs.9 and 10. In these figures, AE amplitude distribution is divided into three regions: low amplitude(0 ~ 2.3mV), middle amplitude(2.3 ~ 5.4mV) and high amplitude(5.4mV ~). The amplitude distribution of both materials was similar, and it was almost the same regardless of the life length. However, it was found that the mode of the damage generating process(matrix cracking, fiber-matrix debonding and fiber breakage) which differentiated based on AE amplitude distribution differed in H material and P material.

Figs.11 and 12 show respectively the relationship AE event count rate and normalized cycles N/N_f (number of cycles N/number of fracture cycles N_f) of the P60 and H60 material, and (a) and (b) are figures in middle amplitude and high amplitude area. And the enlarged view from 0 to 0.9 N/N_f is shown in the figure. In middle amplitude area (a) that corresponds to the fiber-matrix debonding, AE event of H60 material is counted with the load start, and it becomes a minimum near 0.2, it gradually increases afterwards. In high amplitude area (b) which correspond to the fiber breakage, it is not counted with the load start, and it gradually increases after that, and increases rapidly just before fracture. The generation of P60 material of AE in middle amplitude and high amplitude area slowly begins further than H60 material, and it gradually increases after that. In low amplitude area that correspond to the matrix cracking, AE also counted both materials from the load start, and it lowered temporarily, and it gradually increased until the final fracture. Though AE count number of the 20wt.% materials were considerably less than the 60wt.% materials, the developmental process were similar to the 60wt% materials.

4. CONCLUSION

Experiments are carried out to study the effects of matrix resin on mechanical properties, fracture behavior and fatigue behavior of GFRP.

The effects of the elongation property of matrix resin and fiber content on the property of the FRP was clarified. The tensile strength of the ductile matrix resin FRP is higher than that of the brittle one, and however the values of both FRPs with fiber content 20wt.% are lower than those of the neat resins. The values of static and impact fracture toughness(K_s and K_d) increased with increasing fiber content for both resin FRPs. K_d for each neat resin were less than K_s , but K_d for all FRPs used were higher than K_s . Ductile matrix FRP fracture toughness(K_s and K_d) were higher than brittle one. That difference is small under impact test.

Fatigue strength of the 60wt.% FRPs with different resins were similar no matter that the matrix resin is brittle or ductile. However, for the 20wt% FRPs, ductile matrix FRP had higher fatigue strength than that in brittle one.

It was found that the degree of the effect of the property of matrix resin on the FRP varied in loading type and fiber content.

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